

Environment and its influence

Physiological differences in rice desiccation and maturation

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In the USSR, rice is harvested in a period of low temperatures and rains. Therefore, methods to accelerate maturation are being developed and tested. They are desiccation [MgCl_2 solution (0.01%) spray on fully ripened rice] and seniccation [mixture of 2,4-D (0.01%) and $\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2$ (20%) or CO

$(\text{NH}_2)_2$ (20%) solutions on milky-wax ripened rice]. Both methods allow the initiation of harvest 7 days earlier, but the mechanisms differ. Desiccation destroys the cells' ability to hold water, drying and killing the plant's vegetative organs, but it does not change the yield or grain quality. When used to seniccate rice, 2,4-D makes the leaves permeable to inorganic nitrogen or phosphorus, activating the hydrolysis of protoplasmic matters and their movement into the grain (see figure).

Thus seniccation is the artificial accelerator of ripening, which becomes a forced process. Seniccation not only

Seniccation action on the rice leaf.

accelerates ripening, but also increases the yield by 0.3 t/ha (arithmetical mean obtained after 5 years of experiments on a total area of 3,500 ha) and improves grain quality. It increases the 1,000-grain mass and seed germination ability. Thus it is more effective than desiccation. We believe that seniccation followed by desiccation is most effective. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Management and performance of transplanted aus rice in a sample village in Bangladesh

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A monitoring study was conducted on the management and performance of farmers' 1979 aus crop in Salna village, Dacca District. Since the village has irrigation facilities, the major cropping pattern is boro rice-transplanted aman (T. aman) rice. However, some farmers grow local and modern varieties of aus rice in either rainfed or partially irrigated conditions in transplanted aus (T. aus)-T. aman, boro-T. aus, and boro-T. aus-T. aman cropping patterns. Only 12 farmers grew aus rice in the study area and monitoring was through daily record keeping in the fields. Yields were determined by sample crop cutting and expressed in kilograms per hectare at 14% moisture content. The cost and return values were calculated on the basis of actual day-today rates and pri-

Farmers' management practices, yield and returns for the local variety Pukhi and the modern varieties BRI (Chandina), BR3, and BR6 grown as transplanted aus rice in 1979 aus, Salna village, Dacca, Bangladesh.

Item	Aus rice	
	Local	Modern
Samples (%)	33	67
Plowings (av no.)	3	4
Plowings (range)	2-4	3-7
Laddering (av no.)	2	3
Laddering (range)	2-3	2-3
Date of transplanting (av)	19 Jun	12 May
Transplanting date (range)	16-19 Jun	25 Apr-13 May
Av seedling age (days)	27	35
Range of seedling age (days)	25-27	26-61
Farmers who used basal N (%)	100	100
Farmers who used topdressed N (%)	50	75
Av rate of $\text{N-P}_2\text{O}_5\text{-K}_2\text{O}$ (kg/ha)	50-43-0	63-45-0
Farmers who used organic manure (kg/ha)	0	50
Av rate of organic manure (kg/ha)	0	4173
Farmers who irrigated (%)	0	63
Farmers who did not weed (%)	0	25
Farmers who weeded once (%)	25	0
Farmers who weeded twice (%)	75	75
Farmers who used pest control (%)	0	38
Av field duration (days)	70	88
Range of field duration (days)	65-72	75-105
Av yield (t/ha)	2.34	3.76
Range of yield (t/ha)	2.25-2.47	2.42-4.98
Av cost of production (\$/ha)	105.53	142.33
Range of cost of production (\$/ha)	90.07-115.87	91.60-165.66
Av net return (\$/ha)	458.00	845.27
Range of net return (\$/ha)	437.73-482.00	503.73-1163.73

ces prevailing on the farms. The modern varieties (MV) were transplanted earlier, received more irrigation, (see table) received more fertilizer

and organic manure, and, on the average, produced 1.4 t/ha more rough rice than the local variety. Cost of production was \$142.33/ha for MV, \$105.53/ha

for the local variety. On the average, the MV required 18 more days in the field, and gave an increased net return of \$387.27/ha over the local variety.

Announcements

International training on seed technology for vegetable crops offered at UPLB

The Second International Course on Seed Technology for Vegetable Crops for the Asian and Pacific region has been organized by the University of the Philippines at Los Baños (UPLB) in cooperation with the International Agricultural Centre at Wageningen, Netherlands.

The course, which will be held at UPLB from 1 September to 19

November 1981, is primarily for those who are involved in vegetable seed development work and hold a B.S. agricultural degree. The course will concentrate on vegetable crops grown in the Asian and Pacific region.

The First International Course on Seed Technology was held in Wageningen April-June 1980.

For a brochure and application forms, write to: Project Directorate, International Training Programme on Seed Technology, P. O. Box 430, College, Laguna 3720, Philippines. ■

Rice descriptors bulletin available at IRRRI

IRRI has recently published a bulletin on rice descriptors and descriptor-stages, prepared by the Rice Advisory Committee of the International Board for Plant Genetic Resources, under joint IBPGR-IRRI sponsorship.

The bulletin provides explanations, illustrations, and decimal codes for 43 morphoagronomic traits, related grain quality characteristics, and reactions to biotic factors. The publication is essential to systematic characterization of rice cultivars and breeding lines. Its contents

complement the widely used Standard Evaluation System for Rice (now under revision) and help the standardization and computerized processing of crop data.

The bulletin is being sent to major agricultural universities and rice research stations of the world. Libraries that serve rice workers engaged in genetic conservation, plant breeding, and problem-area research may request a complimentary copy from: Genetic Resources Program, International Rice Research Institute, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines. ■

New publication on rice

Rice Cultivation for the Million; Diagnosis and Prescription for Improving Rice Cultivation, by Dr. Seizo Matsushima, was first published in 1966. The book has now been translated into English; 38 previous editions of the Japanese version have been published. *Rice cultivation for the*

million contains new theories and techniques for improving rice cultivation, obtained by the author during 40 years of research.

The new book, published by the Japan Scientific Societies Press, is available in the U. S. and Canada from International Scholarly Book Services (ISBS), 2130 Pacific Avenue, Forest Grove, Oregon 97116, USA. ■

Dr. T. T. Chang, IRRRI geneticist.

T. T. Chang receives International Agronomy Award

The American Society of Agronomy (ASA) awarded the 1980 International Service in Agronomy Award to Dr. T. T. Chang, IRRRI geneticist and leader of IRRRI's Genetic Resources Program, at the Society's annual meeting at Detroit, Michigan, USA.

In honoring Dr. Chang, the ASA recognized his contributions to rice improvement, genetic conservation of rice, and training of young rice scientists on worldwide basis for more than 22 years. In 1978 the ASA elected Dr. Chang as a Society Fellow. In 1969, Mr. H. M. Beachell, Dr. P. R. Jennings, and Dr. Chang shared the John Scott Award of the City of Philadelphia for the development of IR8.

Dr. Chang has served as chairman of the International Board for Plant Genetic Resources (IBPGR)-IRRI Rice Advisory Committee. He is a director of the Society for the Advancement of Breeding and Researches in Asia and Oceania (SABRAO). ■